

Leadership Styles and Service Delivery of Healthcare Institutions

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Abstract

This study examines the impact of leadership styles on the service delivery of healthcare institutions, with a specific focus on secondary hospitals in Nigeria. The objective is to analyze how transformational, transactional, and democratic leadership styles influence the efficiency and quality of healthcare services. The study adopts a conceptual approach to assess leadership effectiveness in hospital settings. Findings reveal that transformational leadership significantly enhances employee motivation and patient satisfaction, while transactional leadership ensures procedural compliance and efficiency. Democratic leadership fosters inclusivity and shared decision-making. However, structural and systemic barriers, such as resource constraints and bureaucratic inefficiencies, were found to hinder the optimal impact of leadership strategies. The study concludes that no single leadership style is universally effective; rather, a hybrid approach that integrates transformational, transactional, and democratic elements is most beneficial. Based on these findings, it is recommended that hospital administrators adopt a flexible leadership model that balances operational efficiency with employee empowerment and patient-centered care, supported by institutional reforms to address systemic challenges.

1. Introduction

Healthcare delivery involves the processes of administering health promotion as well as preventive, diagnostic, therapeutic or rehabilitative services at primary, secondary, tertiary, or quaternary levels (Azeez, 2023). Effective healthcare service delivery ensures that medical care is accessible, affordable and of high quality, one that directly impact the ability to manage and prevent diseases. Ikonnea and Salihub (2022) noted that strengthening healthcare service delivery is crucial to achieving effective interventions and reducing health issues such as child mortality, maternal mortality and the burdens of HIV/AIDS, tuberculosis, malaria and other medical problems that threaten people's lives. Awofeso (2018) asserts that service organizations, such as hospitals, have a mandate and are compelled to concern themselves with quality service delivery because these are the features that define their operations and make them attractive to patients.

Despite the importance of quality healthcare service delivery, significant disparities persist across different regions and countries due to varying social and political factors. These disparities are more common in developing countries (Ganuga & Muhammed, 2022). The World Bank rates healthcare delivery systems in sub-Saharan Africa among the poorest globally (Azeez, 2023). Ayanore et al. (2020) add that healthcare support systems in this region are fragile. As of 2019, while sub-Saharan Africa accounted for 11% of the world's population, its total health spending was merely 1% of the global total (Zekeng, 2019). The World Health Organization recommends a doctor-to-patient ratio of 1:600, but in sub-Saharan Africa, the ratio is alarmingly high at 1:50,000 (Faruk et al., 2020). The limited adoption of advanced technologies further restricts the quality of care provided. Despite increasing investments in the health sector, the persistent epidemics of AIDS, tuberculosis and malaria, coupled with a rising prevalence of non-communicable diseases, have diminished the impact of these investments (Ruxin et al., 2015).

The gap between inputs and outputs in healthcare delivery is often bridged by the leadership of an organization. Abdussalam (2023) asserted that effective leadership is crucial for hospitals to overcome challenges and achieve their healthcare objectives. Literature suggests that certain leadership styles, such as democratic, transformational and

transactional, promote higher job satisfaction and better patient outcomes compared to others (Bamidele et al., 2021). According to Afolabi (2022), one of the factors affecting the delivery of quality health services is leadership style, which can have either a favorable or detrimental impact on staff and, consequently, on the quality of healthcare services provided to patients.

Leadership styles play a significant role in shaping healthcare service delivery by influencing organizational culture and patient care quality. Transformational leadership, for instance, promote an environment of continuous learning, innovation and collaboration among healthcare professionals (Burns, 1978). Leaders who adopt this style inspire and motivate employees by setting a compelling vision and encouraging them to exceed performance expectations (Bass, 1990). In the healthcare sector, transformational leaders are known to improve job satisfaction among staff, which enhances the quality of services provided to patients (Avolio & Yammarino, 2013). Studies have shown that hospitals with transformational leadership experience lower staff turnover rates and higher patient satisfaction (Manning, 2021).

Conversely, autocratic leadership has been associated with reduced employee morale and creativity in healthcare settings (Lewin et al., 1939). While this leadership style may be effective in crisis situations, it often limits healthcare workers' autonomy and reduces job satisfaction (Goleman, 2000). Studies indicate that hospitals where autocratic leadership dominates tend to have higher rates of employee burnout and lower patient satisfaction due to the lack of a participatory decision-making process (Chaudhry & Javed, 2012).

Past studies (including the work of Andrej et al., 2023; Febrian et al., 2023; Kubai, 2023; Kubai et al., 2022; Le et al., 2023; Mohammed & AL-Abrow, 2023; Nderitu & Bula, 2022; Nwankwo et al., 2024; Ogunode et al., 2023; Piwowar-Sulej & Iqbal, 2023; Rojak et al., 2024) have examined the effect of various leadership styles on organizational performance. For instance, studies (e.g., Akdere & Egan, 2020; Aghahowa, 2021; Alrowwad et al., 2020; Cherian et al., 2020; Ferdinan & Lindawati, 2021; Hundie & Habtewold, 2024; Ingsih et al., 2021; Jamali et al., 2023; Saad, 2021) have found a significant relationship between transformational leadership and organizational performance. However, A substantial number of these studies focused on organizational performance in sectors such as education, manufacturing and banking, they neglect healthcare institutions. There has been insufficient focus on the specific aspect of service delivery within these institutions.

Additionally, Elkomy et al. (2023) and Ikonnea and Salihub (2022) assert that the transactional style of leadership is important determinant of service delivery in healthcare institutions. Existing studies (Adam et al., 2020; Alrowwad et al., 2020; Febrian et al., 2022; Le et al., 2023; Nurlina, 2022; Purwanto et al., 2020; Wahyuni et al., 2020; Baig et al., 2021; Hundie and Habtewold, 2024; Thapa and Parimoo, 2022), have established a relationship between the transactional style of leadership and organizational performance. However, studies focusing specifically on healthcare institutions, such as Hundie and Habtewold (2024), Olatoye et al. (2024), and Ikonnea and Salihub (2022), have concentrated on healthcare management in tertiary hospitals. Thus, the current study aims to focus on the service delivery of healthcare institutions, specifically secondary hospitals.

2. Literature Review

2.1 Healthcare Service Delivery

Service delivery in healthcare can be understood differently depending on the perspective and needs of various users, often leading to subjective assessments based on individual experiences and interests at a given time. It encompasses a range of factors, including standards, efficiency, and quality. According to Cao (2018), service delivery can be defined as the extent to which an organization achieves its goals and objectives. It involves the dispensation and provision of services that promote and maintain the health of the people (Azeez, 2023). Health care services entail furnishing of medicine, medical or surgical treatment, nursing care, diagnosis (laboratory and radiation services) dental services, optometry services, complementary services whether or not contingent upon sickness or personal injury. It includes all other and goods with the aim of preventing, alleviating, healing illnesses, physical disability or injuries in persons (Oregon legislature, 2013). Some scholars argue that the quality of service delivery in the public sector can be evaluated using administrative policies and service criteria (Hojat et al., 2011). This concept is directly related to an organization's goals and objectives (Amberkar & Nandit, 2012; Prasad & Dhungana, 2014).

In secondary hospitals, healthcare service delivery involves providing medical attention to patients in need and is characterized by its multidimensional nature. This includes not only curative and preventive care but also health promotion, rehabilitation, and therapeutic services. Ejumudo (2013) describes healthcare services as encompassing all aspects of diagnosing and treating diseases, as well as promoting and maintaining health. Atulomah (2019) adds that effective healthcare delivery includes clinical services, laboratory services, health education, promotion, and the training of health professionals to enhance service effectiveness and efficiency. For healthcare service delivery to be deemed effective, it must integrate these various components into a cohesive system that ensures quality care.

Quality healthcare service delivery, as defined by the WHO (2015), refers to the extent to which healthcare services improve patients' desired health outcomes. Izadi et al. (2017) highlight that the quality of healthcare service delivery impacts patient satisfaction, trust, and perceived value. Al-Damen (2017) underscores that the quality of care significantly influences overall patient satisfaction, with well-managed quality services reducing errors, morbidity, mortality rates, and patient waiting times. This, in turn, positively affects patient satisfaction and encourages continued use of services.

According to Agyapong et al. (2018), the perception of quality in healthcare service delivery is based on how well the services meet or exceed patients' stated and implied needs. Al-Damen (2017) emphasizes that quality service delivery involves applying medical science and technology to maximize health benefits while minimizing risks. WHO (2016) further notes that quality healthcare service delivery relies on physical infrastructure, human resources, knowledge, skills, and the ability to address preventable diseases and complications effectively. Mosadeghrad (2014) points out that quality healthcare service delivery is multidimensional, with various models proposed to evaluate service quality. Hellen (2018) argues that the quality of service delivery is positively correlated with the leadership style within the organization. The quality of healthcare services rendered in secondary healthcare hospitals is largely dependent on some organizational factors that influence the workings of the healthcare system. Venkatesh (2015) noted that quality of care was measured and expressed in quantitative terms using the ranking responses of patient's responses based on experiences they had with healthcare facilities.

2.2 Leadership Styles in Healthcare Institutions

Leadership style refers to the approach a leader takes to provide direction and implement plans in an organizational setting. It encapsulates the typical behaviors and skills a leader exhibits when guiding and supervising employees towards achievement of shared goals (Northouse, 2016). Leadership style develops over time based on a leader's values, experience, personality and situational demands (Gill, 2006). It represents the pattern of actions leaders demonstrate when leading others and can range from highly directive and controlling to fully participative depending on the circumstances. Effective leadership styles are flexible and adaptive to changing team needs and external pressures faced by the organization (Yukl, 2020).

Leadership is a pattern of behavior for leaders to direct and regulate subordinates or subordinates to follow their will in achieving the vision and mission that has been determined (Saputra, 2021). In leadership, a leader uses his influence to motivate group or organization members to achieve organizational goals that have been created. Leadership forms values and culture, communicate organizational goals to members of the organization or group, and provides support to provide examples of the best performance to members as examples or role models. (Saifullah, 2020). A leader in influencing his subordinates or members must use the right and appropriate leadership style so that later the subordinates can be influenced and feel they belong to the company, the leader's philosophy.

Moreover, a leader of an organization must be an expert and apply the appropriate leadership style regarding the situation and the participation of his subordinates (Sudirno & Utama, 2017). Leadership in a professional organization, whether in schools, colleges, or other agencies, has undergone many changes or changes in both leadership styles. Leaders of colleges or schools and even current agencies are more suited to implementing democratic leadership, which can embrace lecturers, educators, committees, student guardians, and the community (Purwanto et al., 2020).

Transformational Leadership

According to Filimonau et al. (2020), transformational leaders boost followers' self-esteem by treating them as individuals and valuing their work. Transition leaders increase their confidence and self-efficacy by making positive (encouraging) appeals (Khan & Khan, 2020). Transformational leadership inspires followers to accomplish goals beyond self-interest through idealized influence, inspirational motivation, intellectual stimulation, and individualized consideration (Bass, 1985). The leader here uses his influencing power and enthusiasm to motivate his followers to work for the benefit of the organization. Leader seeks the requirement for change in the existing organization culture, gives a vision to his subordinates, incorporates mission and implement the change with the dedication of his followers (Robbins & Coulter, 2014).

In transformational leadership, the leader acts as a role model and as a motivator who offers vision, excitement, encouragement, morale and satisfaction to the followers. The leader inspires his people to increase their abilities and capabilities, build up self confidence and promotes innovation in the whole organization (Abdelhelfiz et al., 2015). The better the level of satisfaction among nurses also influences the satisfaction levels among the patients Schreuder et al., (2011). The study done by Abdelhelfiz et al., (2015) in Saudi Arabia showed the highest score received by the transformational style of leadership than transactional and laissez-faire style of leadership. According to Abdelhelfiz et al. (2015), citing Avolio and Bass (2004), a transformational leader is an inspirational leader who promotes encouragement and inspiration among the followers by inculcating a meaning in the assigned work while transactional leaders cater to

followers' immediate self-interest by providing rewards to inspire them. Thus, transformative leaders can increase worker engagement with their supporters by transforming them, several scholars believe that transformative leaders boost followers' self-esteem by treating them as individuals and elevating their work (Hawkes et al., 2021).

Transactional Leadership

According to the study, the transactional leader values hierarchy, order, and structure. This style of Leadership is useful for managing organizations and individuals who cannot handle dynamic work and need potent regulations and frameworks (Bussin et al., 2019). Transactional leaders dislike change, dynamism, and innovation because they resist changes in their work styles. Another study found the organization's current structure and system is not changing with the requirement of time. Here, the objectives and goals are predefined and the leader use rewards and punishment to motivate his followers. Transactional leaders display behaviour associated with constructive and corrective transaction. The constructive style is labelled; 'reward achievement' (contingent reward) and the corrective style is labelled; 'monitors mistakes'- management by exception either active or passive. Prize and penalties are the two major tools used by the leader to inspire his subordinates i.e. if an employee achieves the target within stipulated time, he is given initiative for his work, whereas if the task is not completed within the required time then he will be penalized for the same (Abdelhafiz et al. 2015).The study done in Amman by Abdel hafiz et al., (2015) showed some positive relationship between transactional leadership styles with respect to job satisfaction. Ramey, (2002) in her study in Appalachian state noted that staff nurses working in hospitals perceived transactional leadership style to negatively influence job satisfaction. The findings supported registered staff nurses working in hospitals in this Appalachian state who significantly preferred the transformational leadership style over the transactional leadership style. Whereas transformational leaders uplift morale, motivation and morals of their followers, transactional leaders cater to their followers' immediate self-interest. This type of leader has a strong sense of leadership, authority, and responsibility in their company (Harrison, 2017). Transformational and transactional leadership are two leadership styles often compared. The key difference between them is that transformational leaders inspire and motivate employees to improve their performance, whereas transactional leaders rely on rewards and punishment to control their subordinates. In transactional leadership, employees are expected to follow highly structured rules and regulations, whereas transformational leaders focus on long-term goals and encourage creativity and innovation.

Democratic Leadership

Democratic leadership styles emphasize shared decision-making and active participation from all group members, including employees. Leaders engaging democratic approaches encourage open communication and value input from followers. Employees are involved in the decision-making process through consultation and consensus-building. Authority and power are distributed throughout the group rather than concentrated at the top.

Studies have associated this more inclusive, empowering type of democratic leadership with positive outcomes. Lavanya and Kalliath (2015) surveyed over 300 Indian employees across industries and found higher levels of democratic leadership significantly correlated to increased job satisfaction, organizational commitment, and trust in management. When employees felt their voices were heard and they had ownership over decisions, their intrinsic motivation improved. Similarly, Rafiq et al. (2019) surveyed 104 Pakistani employees from various organizations. They discovered democratic leadership enhanced job satisfaction and reduced burnout by promoting greater inclusion, participation, and empowerment compared to other styles. Employees were reenergized when their competence and ideas were recognized through democratic processes.

Democratic leadership is distinguished by its emphasis on collaboration and collective decision-making, which contrasts sharply with more authoritarian or centralized leadership approaches. Leaders who adopt this style actively seek and value input from their team members, integrating their ideas and feedback into the decision-making process (Rafiq et al. 2019). This participative approach is rooted in the belief that involving team members in decisions not only leverages their diverse expertise and perspectives but also enhances overall engagement and job satisfaction. By creating an environment where team members feel heard and valued, democratic leaders can foster a stronger sense of ownership and commitment to the organization's goals (Grant, 2016).

The process of collaborative decision-making in democratic leadership involves open communication channels and regular consultations with team members. This inclusivity helps build trust and rapport, as team members are more likely to be motivated and invested in the outcomes when they have a stake in the process. Additionally, democratic leadership can enhance team cohesion by aligning individual contributions with collective objectives, thereby reinforcing a shared vision and mutual support among team members. This alignment can lead to more innovative solutions and a more harmonious work environment, as team members feel empowered to contribute their unique skills and perspectives.

In secondary hospitals, where a collaborative approach to patient care and management is essential, the democratic leadership style might significantly enhance healthcare service delivery. By actively involving medical and

administrative staff in decision-making processes, democratic leaders can foster a more inclusive and responsive healthcare environment (Sitienei, et al;2021). This participatory approach allows for diverse perspectives to be considered, which can lead to more comprehensive and patient-centered care plans (Grover, 2022). For instance, incorporating feedback from nurses, physicians, and other healthcare professionals can help identify areas for improvement, streamline processes, and address specific patient needs more effectively. When team members feel their input is valued, they are likely to be more engaged and motivated, which can translate into higher quality care and improved patient outcomes (Wei, 2022).

2.3 Theoretical Perspectives on Leadership and Healthcare Service Delivery

2.3.1 Full Range Leadership Model

Building on Burns' (1978) transformational leadership theory, Bass (1985) formulated the Full Range Leadership Model which proposes a continuum of leadership styles. At one end is active transformational leadership motivating higher effort. Next is transactional leadership based on contingent exchange, and finally passive-avoidant laissez-faire non-leadership (Bass, 1985; Bass & Avolio, 1993).

The model depicts transformational, transactional and laissez-faire leadership discussed in section 2.2.1. It posits transformational leadership elicits highest follower commitment and performance compared to other styles owing to its motivating attributes (Judge & Piccolo, 2004; Lowe *et al.*, 1996). Muenjohn and Armstrong (2008) confirmed the factorial structure and validity of the model measuring the nine leadership factors using the Multifactor Leadership Questionnaire across several cultures. Van der Vyver *et al.* (2014) also verified the three higher-order factors of transformational, transactional, and democratic leadership amongst students and employees in South Africa. The model postulates transformational leadership generates significantly better results than transactional or laissez-faire styles. Several studies established these relationships:

Mustamil *et al.* (2019) found transformational leadership correlated positively to staff retention and financial viability, while passive leadership showed negative associations in Malaysian hospitals. Akter *et al.* (2022) linked transformational styles to clinical quality and governance measures in Nigerian hospitals beyond transactional styles. Braithwaite *et al.* (2020) observed transformational influencing staff morale and performance more so than exchange-based styles in long-term care facilities in Canada. Social exchange theory explains how transformational leaders inspire followers to exert effort beyond expectations by providing vision and empowerment (Bass, 1985). Their charisma and intellectual stimulation foster learning, growth, and performance outcomes (Podsakoff *et al.*, 1990). Contingency perspectives also add that leadership effectiveness depends on contextual fit rather than a universal style (Fiedler, 1967). The model incorporates multiple dimensions capturing a range of contingencies.

2.3.2 Donabedian's Quality of Care Theory

The theoretical and empirical framework of this analysis will be derived from Donabedian's quality of care theory. The concept of delivery of quality healthcare was defined by Avedis Donabedian in his model: Structure, Process-Outcomes. Three quality components are distinguished: technological quality, interpersonal quality and amenities. Professional consistency concerns the effectiveness of treatment in achieving measurable health benefits. Interpersonal quality refers to the patient's needs and preferences accommodation level. Options including physical environment comfort and service structure features are included. He believed that the assessment of healthcare quality would be centered on three elements, namely structure, process and outcome (Donabedian, 1989).

The most relevant aspect of this triad is result because the goals are health services and patients' health status represented in this element. The impact of health care services on the status of a patient's health and the reflection of the patient's health status is known as outcome. Where adequate healthcare is given, the symptoms of the patient's condition will not only decrease, but also complications will be reduced and their ability to cope will be increased; it will therefore be fulfilled (Donabedian, 2016). Therefore, the Donabedian theory for quality of care is pertinent in the implementation of quality systems. It will also ensure that quality efforts get systematically evaluated in order to improve outcomes (Kunkel *et al.*, 2007). This may in turn increase the chance of effective utilization of resources. However, culture has to be encompassed in the process as Donabedian did not include culture in his framework. The institution can develop a culture of quality in their daily operations. Although this theory articulates factors influencing delivery of quality health care, it did not take into account how organizational factors, interpersonal factors, environmental factors and economic factors influence delivery of quality health care which is the focus of the current study.

2.3.3 Systems Theory

Von Bertalanffy first proposed the systems theory in the 1940s, and it was further advanced by (Terreberry, 1968) under the general systems theory, and (Klir, 1991) under aspects of systems science. According to systems theory, a system is made up of multiple components (sub-systems) that work together in harmony. Real systems, in theory, are typically transparent and appear to converse with their surroundings. It goes on to say that the systems theory focuses around

organizations, wholes, as well as systems Swanson, (2001) and encompasses a wide range of disciplines related to parts, wholes, interconnectivity, and organizations, as well as how these disciplines interact with their surroundings.

Furthermore, there is a notion of how organizations must be understood as a system in systems theory. It gives crucial information about organizational behaviors and structures, as well as the processes and nature of system changes, for example, for a deeper understanding (Swanson, 2001). As a result of systems theory, researchers can gain a comprehensive understanding of the fundamental structure of systems, which includes the interrelationship between components and the environment, part 37 arrangement, and the goals of the system's design. Every business is a system. As a result, every action made in the system has the potential to effect people as well as other elements of the system (Wyckoff et al., 1998). Although its idea was originally developed to explain biological notions, it has since been extended to physics, technology, and the social sciences. It is anticipated that the components of the health-care system will work together to ensure that healthcare services are delivered efficiently. Despite its wide applicability, it has not been tested on its suitability on delivery of quality health services in Kenya and specifically Kasarani Sub-County. It was thus used to establish organizational factors, interpersonal factors, environmental factors and economic factors in which delivery of quality health care have an impact.

3. Conceptual Framework

A conceptual framework graphically portrays the theoretical relationships between concepts examined based on literature (Mustamil et al., 2019). This assist investigating hypothesized linkages.

Figure 1: Relationships between leadership styles and healthcare Service delivery

The framework positions transformational, transactional and democratic leadership styles at the initial level based on Bass' continuum (1985). The framework illustrates leadership styles predicting Healthcare service delivery. The framework hypothesizes that leadership styles impact healthcare Service delivery directly as well as indirectly according to supporting literature. For example, Akter et al. (2022) found transformational leadership related to improved staff productivity in Nigerian hospitals both directly and indirectly by enhancing commitment.

According to Judge & Piccolo, (2004) Studies have generally linked transformational leadership positively to trust, effort, commitment, satisfaction and healthcare Service delivery across industries. The framework incorporates these established linkages depicted by one-headed arrows from the literature. By outlining the proposed theoretical model, it contextualizes the need for the current study in examining the relationships in the Nigerian hospital setting. The framework represents original work conceptualizing the constructs and dynamics at play based on an extensive literature review. Translating the concepts into a visual model contributes new knowledge by systematically portraying hypothesized workings to guide investigating leadership impacts.

4. Discussion

Leadership in healthcare institutions is not merely about managerial oversight but fundamentally about building an environment that enhances efficiency and patient satisfaction. Transformational leadership, as highlighted in previous literature, has been associated with improved healthcare outcomes due to its emphasis on motivation and the collective engagement of employees. Leaders who embrace this style inspire their teams by creating a compelling vision and promoting a culture of continuous learning and adaptation. In secondary hospitals, resources are often constrained, transformational leadership is instrumental in navigating these challenges, it instills resilience among staff and ensure that service delivery aligns with best practices. The evidence from this study corroborates findings from prior research

that suggest hospitals with transformational leadership exhibit lower staff turnover rates, higher job satisfaction and improved patient care standards.

Transactional leadership, on the other hand emphasizes compliance, efficiency and task completion through reward and punishment mechanisms. This leadership style ensures that specific operational standards are met. However, it does not always encourage innovation or intrinsic motivation among healthcare professionals. In secondary hospitals, transactional leadership are effective in procedural tasks where consistency and adherence to protocols are essential. However, an overreliance on this approach may lead to rigidity and may limit the healthcare providers' ability to adapt to evolving patient needs. This study suggests that while transactional leadership contributes to operational stability, its effectiveness is maximized when complemented by transformational attributes that encourage staff empowerment and participatory decision-making.

Democratic leadership, which emphasizes shared decision-making and inclusivity, was found to have a positive impact on healthcare service delivery based on the extant literature. This leadership style promote collaboration among healthcare professionals, it ensures that diverse perspectives are considered in decision-making processes. Democratic leadership promotes knowledge-sharing culture and improves problem-solving efficiency. Furthermore, this leadership approach contributes to a positive organizational culture, where healthcare workers feel valued and motivated to contribute meaningfully to service delivery. It is particularly beneficial in environments where patient-centered care is prioritized, as it allows healthcare providers to tailor interventions based on comprehensive input from different stakeholders.

Despite the advantages of these leadership styles, challenges persist in their implementation within secondary hospitals. Structural and systemic barriers, including bureaucratic constraints, limited resources and workforce shortages, they often obstruct the effectiveness of leadership strategies. This study highlights that even the most well-intentioned leadership practices may be undermined by external factors such as inadequate funding, policy inconsistencies and infrastructural deficiencies. Consequently, for leadership styles to yield optimal results, they must be supported by robust institutional frameworks that facilitate seamless healthcare service delivery. Ultimately, the findings of this study reaffirm that no single leadership style is universally superior; rather, a hybrid approach that integrates transformational, transactional and democratic elements may offer the most comprehensive solution for healthcare service delivery. By adopting an adaptive leadership framework, healthcare institutions can balance operational efficiency with employee motivation and innovation.

6. Conclusion

This study's findings indicate a significant and positive effect of transformational, transactional, and democratic leadership styles on healthcare service delivery in institutions within Gombe Metropolis. Each leadership style demonstrated unique contributions to enhancing service quality. Transformational leadership particularly effective in motivating staff to exceed standard expectations through shared goals and a compelling vision. Transactional leadership, with its structured rewards and clear expectations, encouraged compliance and productivity, it helps healthcare providers to meet organizational standards. Democratic leadership, by involving employees in decision-making processes, promoted a collaborative and inclusive environment.

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